

PROJECTIVE DRAWINGS BETWEEN THE INTERSECTION OF DIAGNOSIS & DIALOGICS: THE BIRTH OF A NEW ALLIED DOMAIN PART II

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Figure 4. The Three Processes of Diagnostics

When the two terms *dialogics* and *diagnostics* are brought together into the arena of AAT, they constitute a new allied domain known as dialogic-diagnostic art therapy (DDAT), which is strictly speaking, not AT per se. To elaborate further, DDAT involves a combination of projective drawings done by a client during a dialogic session (counseling) and a follow-up analysis/evaluation of the drawings at four different levels A, B, C and D, as briefly described below, that constitute the Cognition-Conation-Affect-Sensation (CCAS) framework (see Figure 5) used in educational therapy:

Profile. The three key tests whose results are triangulated to determine cognitive functioning level are: DAP-IQ, DAP-SPED and SAEBRS.

- **Level B: Affect/Heart (Emotion)** – The aim is to find out about the client’s emotional state as a follow-up procedure if the result from DaP-SPED is indicative of some emotional disturbance. It may be extended to include administering of Draw-a-Person picking-an-Apple from-a-Tree (DaPpAT) or Draw-a-Person-in-the-Rain (DaPiR). At his second level, examples of projective drawing measures that can be used are: Screening Inventory for Child’s Single Human Figure Drawing (SHFD), which may extend to include Draw-a-Cow, Draw-a-Pig, etc.; Draw-a-Family; and Chromatic analysis (Furth, 1988).

- **Level C: Conation/Strength (Behavior)** – The aim is to find out how the client goes about in response to the current situation s/he has to cope with. Examples of projective drawing measures are: Kinetic House-Tree-Person Drawing (K-HTPD) with/without interview questionnaire (KHTP-Q); Kinetic Family Drawing (KFD) with/without interview questionnaire (KFD-IQ); and chromatic analysis (Furth, 1988). Additional or extended projective drawing tests include Draw-a-Tree (DaT; an alternative choice is Draw-a-Coconut-Tree or DaCT for short), Koch Tree Drawing, Draw-a-House (DaH), Draw-a-Lighthouse (DaLH) and Draw-a-Bridge (DaB), etc.

- **Level D: Psyche/Soul (Self)** – The aim is to determine if the client has challenging issues of concern relating to self (or psyche). It is based administering personality tests to understand the client’s four Jungian archetypes, i.e., persona, shadow, anima and/or animus. The three key tests that are used: a personality test (e.g., Big Five Inventory or BFI for short), the Archetypal Word Association Test (AWAT) and Luscher Color Test (LCT) of personality. Additional projective drawing measures may include Draw-a-Mountain (DaM), Draw-a-River (DaR), Draw-the-Sky (DtS), etc.

The four levels A, B, C and D are summarized in the diagram (see Figure 6) below:

Figure 5. The CCAS Framework used in Educational Therapy

- **Level A: Cognition/Mind** – The aim is to determine a client’s cognitive ability or maturity. Examples of projective drawing measures that are used: Draw-a-Person Intellectual Ability Test for Children, Adolescents & Adults (DAP-IQ) and Draw-a-Person Screening Procedure for Emotional Disturbance (DaP-SPED); and other essential measures include Sensory Profile (SP), Social, Academic & Emotional Behavior Rating Scale (SAEBRS) and Sensory

Figure 1. The 4 Levels of DDAT Administration

Strictly speaking (and we want to reiterate), the DDAT is not AT per se, but an allied domain closer to educational therapy and/or counselling than to art therapy. DDAT is “art-making in therapy” – in Sabados’ (2019, para. 3) own words – that any professional, be s/he an educational therapist, counselor, social worker, psychologist or other mental health worker, who having “attended a class, workshop or training about art therapy, read some books or articles about art therapy, implemented projective drawing assessments, or searched online for art therapy techniques” uses art with his/her clients – and this approach is therapeutic, but not exactly art therapy per se. (Sabados, 2019, para. 3).

However, there is an intersection between AT theory and closely allied domains of specializations (e.g., counseling, special education and psychology, and youth and social work). As such, allied mental health practitioners in these fields often ‘borrow’ from each other. However, Sabados (2019) argued that “just because an art therapist might use a technique designed and used by the social work field does not make them a social worker, nor does it allow them to call the work they’re doing social work” (para. 6). She went on to say: “This effectively reduces an entire profession to some kitschy ‘technique’ one can simply experiment with and feel they understand on the same level as someone who has invested years in training to ethically and effectively implement” (Sabados, 2019, para. 6).

A Brief History behind DDAT

In 2002, DDAT was first introduced in Singapore as Diagnostic Art Therapy (DAT) as a complementary tool to be used with counseling. DAT training was approved by the College of Teachers, London, UK, and offered at two levels: (i) Certificate of Educational Studies (CoES level); and (ii) Diploma of Educational Studies (DoES) which required an additional CoES course in educational counseling with a 1000-word essay. It was taught at the Family Resource and Training Center before being offered at two other private training centers, notably the Creative and Experiential Therapy Institute in 2012. Counselors, social workers, teachers and other interested parties constituted the first few batches of trainees.

Back in 2004, the IACT accepted DDAT as a specialty program and in 2007, it was included “for professional registration, full professional therapist credentialization and board certification” (Chia & Yap, 2008; cited in Chia &

Tong, 2010).

According to Chia and Tong (2010), “[T]he first pioneering batch of seven DDAT professionals completed the specialty program in 2006 and all of them have become very successful practitioners. One therapist moves on to set up her art therapy clinic – ArtsHeal – whose focus is on helping children, adolescents and young adults with socio-emotional behavioral problems as well as mental disturbances” (p. 15). Another therapist returned to Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, to head a counseling center in 2006. The third therapist continues to use DDAT as a school counselor. The fourth used it to help her students at a student care center which she founded. The fifth therapist went on to become a DDAT instructor training parents to use DDAT to understand their children and themselves better. The remaining two therapists had their own private practice until they retired quite recently. Among them, two went on to become registered DDAT practitioners and only one went on to obtain her board certification.

Conclusion

The specialty program of DDAT has since evolved to include new topics with case studies involving administration of different projective drawing measures (especially DaP, HTP and KFD). It has incorporated Gerard Egan’s (2002) Skilled Helper Model of eclectically based counseling to provide a structured and solution focused basis for counsellors and therapist. It is a three-stage model where each state consists of specific skills that a therapist uses to help a client move forwards. The counseling model has empowered counselors and therapists to increase their efficiency and structure their work in a more logical way, and so helping their clients in a more consistent manner and being less reliant upon their fluctuating ‘therapeutic inspiration’.

Many of the DDAT graduates have done their own research, presented their DDAT practice at webinars, seminars and conferences, wrote and published articles on DDAT in social media, newsletters and journals.

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